

 Ref. Ares(2022)3928809 - 25/05/2022
HORIZON 2020
FRAMEWORK PROGRAMME
Research and Innovation Action

Deliverable – D77 (D26.5)

Data exchange standards for dataset exchange and analysis

WP26: JRA1 – Maximizing the output of fragment screening

Grant Agreement number	871037
Project acronym	iNEXT-Discovery
Project title	Infrastructure for transnational access and discovery in structural biology
Due Date	M24 (January, 2022)
Delivery Date	M28 (May, 2022)
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D77 (D26.5): Data exchange standards for dataset exchange and analysis

Lead beneficiary: NKI

Involved partners: NKI, EMBL-GR, DIAMOND, HZB, MAX IV, EMBL-EBI

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1 Summary

This deliverable D26.5 from JRA1 (WP26 - Maximizing the output of fragment screening) describes a set of data exchange standards to support the creation of flexible workflows in crystallographic fragment screening. Each step between initial data collection and final deposition of a refined model structure of an individual sample or of an entire screen can be performed by one or more processors at the different screening facilities, and even off-site. To ensure compatibility between those processors, essential (meta-)data for each step are defined, together with community-standard FAIR data formats. The control and data management of screen data analysis is done from within a screening facility to make sure that all relevant (meta-)data are stored at a single site until the entire screen data is deposited.

2 Realisation of the deliverable

At the start of the iNEXT-Discovery project a 'Crystallographic Data Management working group' was formed for discussing together the standards that could be used internationally for exchanging data from crystallographic fragment screening. This working group consists of several delegates from crystallographic screening facilities as well as from EBI, well-known experts in data management and also hosting the European interface to the PDB. The members of this group are:

- Robbie P. Joosten Netherlands Cancer Institute (NKI)
- Tyler Gorrie-Stone Diamond Light Source (DIAMOND)
- Raphael Bourgeois EMBL Grenoble (EMBL-GR)
- Sameer Velankar Protein Data Bank Europe (EMBL-EBI)
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- Manfred S. Weiss Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin (HZB)
- Elmir Jagudin MAX IV Laboratory (MAX IV)
- Tobias Krojer MAX IV Laboratory (MAX IV)

Deliberations between the different stakeholders are being performed online and via email in whole-group and in bilateral discussions.

3 Data flow in crystallographic fragment screening

The process of crystallographic fragment screening can be divided into several distinct steps, which can either be performed at the site of data collection (such as a screening facility) or off-site. In this iNEXT-Discovery activity we distinguish the following stages (Figure 1):

- Crystallographic data collection and processing
- Fragment fitting
- Model optimisation
- Hit analysis
- Deposition
 - To the screen repository
 - To the Protein Data Bank

Most of these steps in the process use multiple non-exclusive processors that perform the computational workload within them. To achieve optimal modularity and thus flexibility for the user in the way these processors are interconnected, standards must be set for the exchange of (meta-)data between them. These (meta-)data contain (i) the experimental data

of the fragment screen, (ii) suitable and sufficient descriptors of the experimental conditions, (iii) models of the experimental data and (iv) provenance tracking. In addition to using processors, users may want to process their screening data locally. Therefore, export and import data formats and standards must also be carefully defined.

(Meta-)data exists both at the individual sample level (i.e. the data associated with a crystal) and at the screening level. Here, in terms of design of data exchange requirements we primarily focus on the sample level. These sample data can then subsequently be encapsulated in a combined screen that includes metadata that describes all samples and the parameters describing the screening campaign itself. To avoid unnecessary data transfer, it will be allowed to transfer the data of a subset of all samples, provided that the metadata for the entire screen is transferred or linked through a persistent identifier. For example, we envisage that only samples with fragment hits will be transferred for follow-up model optimization.

Using this overall framework, we focus on a minimal amount of (meta-)data to be passed between the processors. This is possible because screening facilities are often used as a central hub for process control, data management, and provenance tracking. That is, all processing phases are initiated from the screening facilities, and also all (meta-)data created by the processors flow back to the screening facilities. The technical process of data exchange is not elaborated in this Deliverable-document but the need for security upon data exchange (e.g. through authentication) is noted. To enable efficient implementation of data exchange, a form of federated authentication, e.g. through Instruct-ERIC's research administration system ARIA¹, is recommended.

The final output of a crystallographic fragment screen campaign will be deposited in a designated 'fragment screen repository', which will be the topic of Deliverable D26.10 due on January 2023. The exact data that will be deposited for any campaign is therefore not completely defined yet in current document.

Figure 1: Graphic description of the fragment screening process and data flow. The screening data is initially collected at research facilities. The data moves through the different stages of fragment screening thereby gradually accumulating (meta-)data. In each stage, the screen can be enriched by one or more processors. Data is transferred as a complete screen where possible, except in the case of PDB deposition. There reference to the entire screen is passed as metadata.

4 Exchange standards

In the following, we describe minimal requirements for the data exchange events that we foresee, inherently implying that supplying more (meta-)data to a processor is allowed. Any input (meta-)data that is not actively used by a processor should either be passed on to its output without modification, or be re-merged from the original data source.

4.1 Agreed exchange standards

In accordance with national, European and international community standards and best practices, all data transfers should adhere to the FAIR principle². This entails that all data should be stored in well-supported, community-standard formats.

For crystallographic model coordinates and reflection data this is currently the mmCIF format³, as these can be richly annotated and even required for deposition. For practical reasons, however, intermediate data transfers of diffraction data is done in MTZ format⁴. Obviously, this is linked to a specific mmCIF file at the processing hub. Electron density maps are presented as map coefficients.

To avoid compatibility issues and complexity in the final deposition step, we recommend that all fragments forming a screening library are described by an optional stereo SMILES string⁵, an InChi key⁶ and a residue identifier from the Protein Data Bank Chemical Component Dictionary⁷ if one is available. New compounds can always be pre-registered at the wwPDB to obtain a unique residue identifier. Otherwise, the identifier should be set to one of the names that are reserved for this by the wwPDB (LIG, INH, DRG, and 01-99). The data should be presented in an mmCIF formatted restraint file as this is compatible with all major crystallographic software packages. Other restraints, e.g. for compounds and covalent linkages that are already modelled in the apo-structure of the target, should also be provided in mmCIF format.

All other (meta-)data that cannot be captured in the formats above must be passed on using JSON format. A description of the keys in this file, a JSON schema, will be made publicly available online. The data processors will collaborate with the wwPDB to integrate this data into the mmCIF-PDBx standard as much as possible. As an intermediate measure the data can be cast into a separate mmCIF category.

4.2 Data for fragment fitting

At the moment there are several processors that perform fragment fitting, such as RHOFIT⁸, PanDDA⁹, and PDB-REDO¹⁰. Minimal requirements for all of these are (i) an apo-structure, (ii) accompanying reflection data and (iii) a description of the fragment(s) that should be fitted. Table 1 describes details of required and optional (meta-)data that can be used in processing. The output that flows back to the screening facility is described in Table 2.

Table 1: Required and optional (meta-)data for fragment fitting

Data item	Description	Key metadata
Sample identifier	Required: Name used for the sample; must be unique within the screen.	
Screen identifier	Required: Name of screen of which the sample is a part; must be globally unique.	
Sample sequence	Required: Amino acid sequence of sample in Fasta format.	

Apo-structure	Required: Atomic model coordinates of the macromolecule(s) that was crystallised.	Status flag: The apo-structure is already fitted to the reflection data ^a .
Reflection data	Required: Crystallographic data that can be used to create electron density maps for fitting. This could be more than one set, e.g. because of data processing with several pipelines.	Identifiers of the datasets and description which data labels represent F_{obs}/I_{obs} and $\sigma F_{obs}/\sigma I_{obs}$.
Anomalous reflection data	Optional: Crystallographic data that can be used to create anomalous difference maps to validate fragment with anomalous scatterers.	Description which data labels represent anomalous data.
Map coefficients	Optional: Coefficients for an electron density map that can be used for fragment fitting.	Description which data labels represent amplitude and phase.
Fragment description	Required: Chemical description of the fragment(s) used in the sample.	Residue identifier.
Crystallisation mixture	Required: Description of other compounds (buffers, cryoprotectant, solvents, ...) in the sample.	PDB residue names.
Restraints	Optional: Geometric restraints for non-standard compounds or linkages other than the fragment.	N/A

^a If not, molecular replacement must be performed

Table 2: Required and optional (meta-)data returned from fragment fitting

Data item	Description	Key metadata
Sample identifier	Required: Name used for the sample; must be unique with in the screen.	
Screen identifier	Required: Name of screen of which the sample is a part; must be globally unique.	
Fitted structure	Required: Atomic model coordinates of the macromolecule(s) with fitted fragments including the amino acid sequence of the sample.	Number of fragments fitted.
Used data set	Required: Description of which data set is used for fitting.	Description of data columns used in data set.
Fitting metrics	Optional: Critical scores for fragment fitting decision.	References to individual fragments.
Restraints	Optional: Geometric restraints for non-standard compounds or linkages merged with fragment restraints.	N/A

4.3 Data for model optimisation

Structural model optimization can occur before and/or after fragment fitting to improve map quality, or to polish a model after an initial fitting of a fragment. Table 3 describes data items that are relevant as input of model optimisation in PDB-REDO¹¹; Table 4 describes the output.

Table 3: Required and optional (meta-)data for model optimisation

Data item	Description	Key metadata
Sample identifier	Required: Name used for the sample; must be unique with in the screen.	
Screen identifier	Required: Name of screen of which the sample is a part; must be globally unique.	
Model coordinates	Required: Atomic model coordinates of the macromolecule(s) that was crystallised with or without fitted ligands.	Amino acid sequence of the crystallised construct.

Reflection data	Required: Crystallographic data that can be used to perform model refinement. Could be more than one data set.	Identifiers of the datasets and description which data labels represent F_{obs}/I_{obs} and $\sigma F_{obs}/\sigma I_{obs}$.
Restraints	Required: Geometric restraints for all non-standard compounds or linkages including the fragment. This can be either part of the coordinate file or presented as a separate file.	N/A
Anomalous reflection data	Optional: Crystallographic data that can be used to create anomalous difference maps to validate fragment anomalous scatterers.	Description which data labels represent anomalous data.
Crystallisation mixture	Required: Description of other compounds (buffers, cryoprotectant, solvents, etc) that may be in the sample.	PDB residue names.

Table 4: Required and optional (meta-)data returned from model optimisation

Data item	Description	Key metadata
Sample identifier	Required: Name used for the sample; must be unique with in the screen.	
Screen identifier	Required: Name of screen of which the sample is a part; must be globally unique.	
Model coordinates	Required: Atomic model coordinates of the optimized model.	Amino acid sequence of the crystallised construct. Status flag: model coordinates were changed. Description of model changes including added/deleted residues).
Used data set	Required: Description of which data set was used for model optimisation.	Description of data columns used in data set.
Map coefficients	Optional: Crystallographic data that can be used to produce electron density maps.	Description of available maps and which data labels represent map amplitude and phase.
Restraints	Required: Geometric restraints for all non-standard compounds or linkages including the fragment.	N/A

4.4 Data for model analysis

Model analysis can be performed at the sample level, but analysis of an entire screen at once produces important additional insight. Model analysis has a very broad scope in tools like Fragalysis¹², that includes simple visual inspection but also more systematic computational analysis. As the output of model analysis varies greatly, it may not be fed back into the screening data. Therefore, it makes sense to only consider input data as defined in Table 5.

Table 5: Required and optional (meta-)data for model analysis

Data item	Description	Key metadata
Sample identifier	Required: Name used for the sample; must be unique with in the screen.	
Screen identifier	Required: Name of screen of which the sample is a part; must be globally unique.	
Model coordinates	Required: Atomic model coordinates of the macromolecule(s) with fitted ligands.	References to fitted ligands.
Sample sequence	Required: Sequence of sample in Fasta format.	

Fitting metrics	Optional: Critical scores for fragment fitting decision.	References to individual fragments.
Reflection data	Optional: Crystallographic data that can be used to generate electron density maps.	Identifiers of the datasets and description which data labels represent F_{obs}/I_{obs} and $\sigma_{Fobs}/\sigma_{Iobs}$.
Map coefficients	Optional: Coefficients for electron density maps. Different map types to consider: 2mFo-DFc, mFo-DFc and anomalous maps of the current model; map used for fragment fitting.	Description which data labels represent amplitude and phase.

4.5 Data for deposition

We describe two types of deposition: the deposition of data for individual samples to the Protein Data Bank (PDB), and that of an entire screen to a ‘fragment screen repository’. Setting the standards for deposition of whole screens is work in progress, and these will be described in deliverable D26.10 later on in the iNEXT-Discovery project. Deposition to the PDB uses a well-defined standard that has been set by the wwPDB partners and that includes all required (meta-)data¹³. In addition to the (meta-)data that are strictly required by the PDB, we recommend deposition of all additional (meta-)data that can be captured in the mmCIF format. This should include but is not limited to a detailed description of the crystallisation mixture and cryoprotectant, anomalous reflection data, a direct reference (persistent identifier) to the screen that is performed at the research facility, and references to diffraction images. In addition, all processors involved in the creation of the final structure model should be referenced in the coordinate mmCIF file.

4.6 Data for export

Export of data outside of the screening facilities’ project management systems can occur for several reasons, and this means that different types of data can be collected by researchers, depending on the use case. A minimal requirement for any export event is that all data should be accompanied by the metadata that refer to the particular screen and specific sample from which the data is exported. There should also be a straightforward way of exporting all (meta-)data associated with a sample. For this, it is important that all these data are presented in well-described FAIR formats.

4.7 Data for import

Likely, there will be cases where previously exported data or other relevant (meta)data is fed back into the project management system for a screen, for instance when a structure model is manually polished locally by a user before being sent to any of the processors. In such cases, the data that is imported must be carefully associated to the existing data, with a clear provenance record allowing the source and history of the data to be stored in the project management system.

4.8 Data standards for screens

Any fragment screening campaign is to be considered a single experiment using a large set of samples (i.e. crystals with or without a soaked compound). In the context of data transfer we can perceive such a screen as a container for all samples with additional overarching metadata

describing the set of samples and the overall features of the screen (e.g. the screen library that was used). In data transfer it is important that the integrity of each screen is maintained, at the same time we recognise that it is conceivable that not all sample data in a screen needs transfer to processors. For instance, model coordinates and diffraction data for samples without a soaked fragment need not be subject to fragment fitting. We therefore recommend that when screens are transferred, metadata describing all samples is enclosed with specific flags that indicate whether sample data is also transferred within the screen container (for integrity checking). This metadata should also describe which samples are to be processed and which not. After processing, the returning (meta-)data should follow the same rules.

5 Extensions and format updates

This deliverable describes our community recommendations for data exchange in the context of crystallographic fragment screening in its current practise. It is highly likely that due to improvements of computational methods and data capture, additional types of (meta-)data will emerge. Where suitable and possible, these will be added to the mmCIF format dictionary that is maintained by the wwPDB. Descriptions of new data that are not being captured in mmCIF files can be added to the online JSON description and may temporarily be added as a separate mmCIF category for later integration into the general mmCIF PDBx dictionary.

An example of such foreseeable extension is the linking of fragment screening campaigns that are done with identical specimen (e.g. the same protein target or target/fragment combination) through a variety of different experimental approaches such as NMR and biophysical measurements.

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